

Mechanical properties and energy absorption capability of hybrid honeycomb superstructure

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Structural design and analysis model

Fig. 1. Geometric illustrations of the proposed hierarchical auxetic-hexagonal honeycombs: (a) Regular auxetic-hexagonal honeycomb (AuxHex); (b) Triangular hierarchical auxetic-hexagonal honeycomb (T-AuxHex); (c) Double arrowhead hierarchical auxetic-hexagonal honeycomb (A-AuxHex).

Fig. 2. Area illustrations of the AuxHex honeycombs: (a) AuxHex; (b) T-AuxHex; (c) A-AuxHex.

$$\bar{\rho} = \rho^* / \rho = \frac{S - (S_1 + S_2 + 4S_3) - S_4}{S}$$

$$S = \sqrt{3}h_1(h_1 + h_2 + 2h_3)$$

$$S_1 = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \left[h_1 - \frac{t}{\sqrt{3}} \right]^2$$

$$S_2 = \sqrt{3} \left[(n_1 - 1)l_1 - \frac{t}{\sqrt{3}} \right] \left[h_1 - \sqrt{3}T - \left(h_1 - \frac{t}{\sqrt{3}} \right) / 2 \right]$$

$$S_3 = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \left[h_1 - \frac{t}{\sqrt{3}} \right] \left[h_1 - \frac{2T}{\sqrt{3}} \right]$$

$$S_4 = \sqrt{3} \left[(n_1 - 1)l_1 - \frac{t}{\sqrt{3}} \right] \left[(n_1 - 2)l_1 - \frac{2T}{\sqrt{3}} \right]$$

$$S_5 = \sqrt{3} \left[h_1 - \frac{t}{\sqrt{3}} \right] \left[h_1 - \frac{2T}{\sqrt{3}} \right]$$

$$S_6 = \sqrt{3} \left[(n_1 - 1)l_1 - \frac{t}{\sqrt{3}} \right] \left[(n_1 - 3)l_1 - \sqrt{3}T - \left((n_1 - 1)l_1 - \frac{t}{\sqrt{3}} \right) / 2 \right]$$

$$S_7 = \sqrt{3} \left[(n_1 - 1)l_1 - \frac{t}{\sqrt{3}} \right] \left[(n_1 - 2)l_1 - \frac{2T}{\sqrt{3}} \right]$$

$$S_8 = \sqrt{3} \left[(n_1 - 1)l_1 - \frac{t}{\sqrt{3}} \right] \left[(n_1 - 2)l_1 - \frac{2T}{\sqrt{3}} \right]$$

$$S_9 = \sqrt{3} \left[(n_1 - 1)l_1 - \frac{t}{\sqrt{3}} \right] \left[(n_1 - 2)l_1 - \frac{2T}{\sqrt{3}} \right]$$

$$S_{10} = \sqrt{3} \left[(n_1 - 1)l_1 - \frac{t}{\sqrt{3}} \right] \left[(n_1 - 2)l_1 - \frac{2T}{\sqrt{3}} \right]$$

$$S_{11} = \sqrt{3} \left[(n_1 - 1)l_1 - \frac{t}{\sqrt{3}} \right] \left[(n_1 - 2)l_1 - \frac{2T}{\sqrt{3}} \right]$$

$$S_{12} = \sqrt{3} \left[(n_1 - 1)l_1 - \frac{t}{\sqrt{3}} \right] \left[(n_1 - 2)l_1 - \frac{2T}{\sqrt{3}} \right]$$

$$S_{13} = \sqrt{3} \left[(n_1 - 1)l_1 - \frac{t}{\sqrt{3}} \right] \left[(n_1 - 2)l_1 - \frac{2T}{\sqrt{3}} \right]$$

$$S_{14} = \sqrt{3} \left[(n_1 - 1)l_1 - \frac{t}{\sqrt{3}} \right] \left[(n_1 - 2)l_1 - \frac{2T}{\sqrt{3}} \right]$$

$$S_{15} = \sqrt{3} \left[(n_1 - 1)l_1 - \frac{t}{\sqrt{3}} \right] \left[(n_1 - 2)l_1 - \frac{2T}{\sqrt{3}} \right]$$

$$S_{16} = \sqrt{3} \left[(n_1 - 1)l_1 - \frac{t}{\sqrt{3}} \right] \left[(n_1 - 2)l_1 - \frac{2T}{\sqrt{3}} \right]$$

$$S_{17} = \sqrt{3} \left[(n_1 - 1)l_1 - \frac{t}{\sqrt{3}} \right] \left[(n_1 - 2)l_1 - \frac{2T}{\sqrt{3}} \right]$$

$$S_{18} = \sqrt{3} \left[(n_1 - 1)l_1 - \frac{t}{\sqrt{3}} \right] \left[(n_1 - 2)l_1 - \frac{2T}{\sqrt{3}} \right]$$

$$S_{19} = \sqrt{3} \left[(n_1 - 1)l_1 - \frac{t}{\sqrt{3}} \right] \left[(n_1 - 2)l_1 - \frac{2T}{\sqrt{3}} \right]$$

$$S_{20} = \sqrt{3} \left[(n_1 - 1)l_1 - \frac{t}{\sqrt{3}} \right] \left[(n_1 - 2)l_1 - \frac{2T}{\sqrt{3}} \right]$$

$$E_1 = 4E_1 \frac{T^3 \cos \theta}{L^2 (h_1 + h_2 + 2h_3) \sin^2 \theta}$$

$$E_2 = 4 \frac{(N\sqrt{3}l_1 + \alpha t)^2 \cos \theta (2\sqrt{3}l_1 - 3t)}{L^2 (h_1 + h_2 + 2h_3) \sin^2 \theta} E_1$$

$$E_3 = \frac{3(7\sqrt{3} + 6) \left[\frac{N\sqrt{3}l_1 + \alpha t}{L} \right]^2 \cos \theta t E_1}{14 L^2 (h_1 + h_2 + 2h_3) \sin^2 \theta}$$

$$\left(\sigma_{1y} \right)_p = \frac{1}{2L} \frac{h_1 + h_2}{(h_1 + h_2) L + \sin \theta} \frac{T^2}{L^2} \sigma_{1y}$$

$$\left(\sigma_{1y} \right)_p = \frac{1}{2L} \frac{h_1 + h_2}{(h_1 + h_2) L - \sin \theta} \frac{T^2}{L^2} \sigma_{1y}$$

$$\left(\sigma_{1y} \right)_p = \frac{1}{2L} \frac{h_1 + h_2}{(h_1 + h_2) L + \sin \theta} \frac{T^2}{L^2} \sigma_{1y}$$

$$\left(\sigma_{1y} \right)_p = \frac{1}{2L} \frac{h_1 + h_2}{(h_1 + h_2) L - \sin \theta} \frac{T^2}{L^2} \sigma_{1y}$$

$$h_1 = L = (n + N)l_1, \quad h_2 = (n + 2N)l_1, \quad h_3 = L = (n + N)l_1, \quad h_4 = (n + 2N)l_1$$

$$h_2 = (2n + 3N)l_1, \quad T = N\sqrt{3}l_1 + t, \quad h_2 = (2n + 3N)l_1, \quad T = N\sqrt{3}l_1 + t$$

◆ To accurately calculate the relative density of the hierarchical AuxHex honeycombs, the volume of the voids is subtracted from the total volume of the unit cell to obtain the volume of the material. This method avoids errors due to the overlap of materials at the nodes, which is significant for hierarchical structures. The relative density expressions of the three AuxHex honeycombs are shown in (a), (b) and (c) on the right;

◆ Assumed that the cell walls are Euler-Bernoulli beams by neglecting the shear deformation of the beam and ignoring the axial extension or compression deformation. That is to say, only bending of the cell walls of the structures is considered under small deformations.

Experimental tests and finite element modeling

Fig. 3. Test specimens: (a-b) 3D-printed regular AuxHex, T-AuxHex and A-AuxHex honeycombs; (c) 3D-printed uniaxial tensile specimens for experimental tests.

Three types of hierarchical honeycomb and uniaxial tensile specimens were fabricated using 304 stainless steel by selective laser melting (SLM) technique. Quasi-static uniaxial compression tests were respectively performed on the hierarchical honeycomb specimens, using an electronic universal testing machine;

To evaluate the macroscopic compressive response and reveal the deformation mechanism of hierarchical structures, finite element simulations were performed. A series of 3D FE models were created according to the geometrical size of panels.

Fig. 5. Comparison of the stress-strain curves obtained from the experiments and FE simulations: (a) AuxHex; (b) T-AuxHex; (c) A-AuxHex.

Name	n ₁	n ₂	l ₁ (mm)	t ₁ (mm)	$\bar{\rho}$	L ₁ (mm)	H ₁ (mm)	T ₁ (mm)
AuxHex	5	11	6	4	3.8	24.92%	224	39
T-AuxHex	5	11	6	4	0.71	26.05%	224	43
A-AuxHex	5	11	6	4	0.5	26.15%	224	43

Fig. 4. Experimental setup of the hierarchical honeycombs under axial compressive loading.

Fig. 6. Comparison of the experiments and FE simulations results: (a) modulus; (b) strength.

Results

In-plane compressive response

Fig. 7. Comparison of the deformations obtained from the experiment and the FE analysis: (a) AuxHex; (b) T-AuxHex; (c) A-AuxHex. (Here ϵ denotes the nominal compressive strain)

Fig. 8. The specific modulus and specific collapse stress of the three types of AuxHex honeycombs.

Compared to the AuxHex honeycombs, the specific modulus of the T-AuxHex honeycombs and the A-AuxHex honeycombs are increased by 184.7% and 47.2%, respectively. And the specific collapse stresses are increased by 54.1% and 14.3%, respectively.

Energy absorption capability of the three type structures

Fig. 9. Comparison of energy absorption capacity of the compression experiments of hierarchical honeycombs: (a) densification strain; (b) collapse stress; (c) specific energy absorption (SEA) and (d) effectiveness of energy absorption (EEA).

Table 2. Comparison of the experiments and FE simulations results of mechanical properties of the hierarchical AuxHex honeycombs

Honeycombs	Num.-1	Num.-2	Num.-3	Average	FEA	Error
AuxHex	Modulus 1655.7	1696.3	---	1676	1701.9	1.55
AuxHex	Strength 23.42	23.66	---	23.54	25.69	9.13
T-AuxHex	Modulus 4665.5	4677.2	4341.2	4561.3	4416.8	-3.17
T-AuxHex	Strength 34.30	34.75	35.00	34.68	38.30	10.43
A-AuxHex	Modulus 2385.3	2296.3	2421.8	2367.8	2575.4	8.77
A-AuxHex	Strength 26	25.57	25.9	25.82	28.00	8.43

✓ Plastic collapse stress reflects the ability of the structures to withstand loads;
✓ EEA reflects the effective utilization of the volume of the structures under compression.

Discussion

Effect of geometrical parameters on mechanical properties

Fig. 10. The configurations of hierarchical AuxHex honeycombs with N=1, 2 and 3: (a) T-AuxHex; (b) A-AuxHex. Here $n=6$, $l=3$ mm, $t=0.5$ mm.

Fig. 11. The configurations of hierarchical AuxHex honeycombs with $n=2$, 4 and 6: (a) T-AuxHex; (b) A-AuxHex. Here $N=1$, $l=4$ mm, $t=0.5$ mm.

Fig. 12. Effect of the length of substructures on the modulus and collapse stress of the hierarchical honeycombs: (a) T-AuxHex; (b) A-AuxHex. Here $N=1$, $n=4$, $t=0.5$ mm.

Fig. 13. Effect of the thickness of substructures on the modulus and collapse stress of the hierarchical honeycombs (a) T-AuxHex; (b) A-AuxHex. Here $N=1$, $n=4$, $l=4$ mm.

Fig. 14. Effect of the number of layers of substructures on the modulus and collapse stress of the hierarchical honeycombs: (a) T-AuxHex; (b) A-AuxHex. Here $n=6$, $l=3$ mm, $t=0.5$ mm.

Fig. 15. Effect of the number of substructures along the length of the cell walls on the modulus and collapse stress: (a) T-AuxHex; (b) A-AuxHex. Here $N=1$, $l=4$ mm, $t=0.5$ mm.

◆ The results show that the in-plane bearing and energy absorption properties of hybrid honeycomb superstructures are greatly improved under the same areal density and loading conditions. The Young's modulus and strength of the AuxHex structure with triangular sub-structure (T-AuxHex) increased by 170% and 47%, respectively, and the Young's modulus and strength of the AuxHex structure with arrow-shaped sub-structure (A-AuxHex) increased by 39% and 9%, respectively. In addition, the specific energy absorption (SEA) of the T-AuxHex is about 1.5 times that of the A-AuxHex;

◆ Therefore, the T-AuxHex has excellent in-plane bearing and energy absorption properties. Excellent energy absorption, internal space fillability and lightweight performance make hybrid honeycomb superstructures suitable for lightweight/high-impact protection structures in the future.